

EXPLICATING NARRATIVE TECHNIQUES IN AMISH TRIPATHI'S *IMMORTALS OF MELUHA*

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Abstract:

Among the numerous innate human traits is the ability to tell stories. This paper aims to elucidate the narratological techniques in Amish Tripathi's *Immortals of Meluha*. The study discusses various narrative devices in both Indian and Western outlooks. Moreover, it briefs the selected work for study in a nutshell. Finally, the paper concentrates on how Amish Tripathi has fused both devices in the chosen text. It emphasises the impacts of unlearning and ignoring the native traditions.

Keywords: Narratology, Western Narrative devices, Indian Narrative Models, Itihasas, Puranas.

Storytelling and gossiping are the innate qualities that human beings possess. Owing to these peculiar qualities, our ancestors have created multiple stories based on actions performed by legends. As it is believed, the universe is created cyclically. Hence, things happen to everyone, but how they deal with the situations is the lesson to be learned for the younger generations. The stories of these legends are restored in the scriptures. The intellectual writers narrate these legendary stories entwined with information on various areas of knowledge such as geography, sciences, war strategies, and many others. On the philosophical level, it also deals with the concepts related to spiritual understanding. The study of such multiple structures is classified under narratology. The term narratology is usually identified with stalwarts like Gerard Genette, Gerald Prince, Roland Barthes, etc. However, the word is not confined only to western society. It is a shared attribute among human beings, as every culture has its own unique tradition in displaying its heritage. Though every culture has its uniqueness in its practices, it also shares some similarities. Indian narrative devices also share some of the peculiar qualities that are discussed by Western intellectuals. The present paper explores the narrative techniques adopted by the author in his debut novel, *Immortals of Meluha*. The insights drawn from various resources ensure his knowledge of ancient scriptures of India, apart from throwing a considered light on our rich cultural heritage and tradition. Firstly, the paper details the Western and Indian narrative techniques and later introduces the author. Finally, it summarises and analyses the chosen text.

The term narratology is defined as “the science of narrative”. The term is generally popularised by structuralist critics limiting it to their tenets. However, the term has been to post-structuralist critics too. Theorists like Tzvetan Todorov, Mikhail Bakhtin, Vladimir Propp, Gerard Genette, Mieke Bal, Gerald Prince, and Roland Barthes are some of the major figures. In the contemporary era, narratology is a broader term as it includes both non-literary genres and discourses apart from literary texts and works. Hence, any piece of work, either oral or written is deemed a narrative. It can be a representation of individuals’ thoughts and understanding of the events based on their perception. The narrative is mostly analysed based on two factors. They are linguistic and semiotic representations. It studies the structure, representation, and the plot construction. It also focuses on the horizontal and vertical approaches while analysing the events. Though the theorists confine to a particular aspect, it is indeed efficient to note that the other aspects are equally potent in the process of creating a work. Thus, both concepts are intertwined with one another. The term narratology has been defined by various academicians and critics in various ways. Bal has defined, “*Narratology* as a field of study is the ensemble of theories of narratives, narrative texts, images, spectacles, events- of cultural artefacts that tell a story.” (Bal2, 3). He emphasises that narrative can be analysed based on fabula, story, and texts. Some are presented to the listener as per the understanding of the narrator rather than its authenticity, as Prince opines. Hence multiple narratives emerge on any account based on the idea or the perception of the event they chose to narrate. The difference in narratives might emphasise the chosen themes such as history, power structures, cultural differences, victimisation, gender bias, psychoanalysis, ecocritical, and so on. The concept, narratology, includes all the aspects dealt with in the novel not excluding even the minute details of the narration. It depends on the critic who takes his stand in describing the importance of the aspect that s/he has chosen. Some discuss the importance of linguistic elements of the novel, whereas others confine themselves to concentrating on the techniques employed by the author while narrating the text. It also emphasises on the perspective of patterns, motifs, themes and how they are interwoven in the narration.

India is a home for multiculturalism. Every culture has its history, traditions, and beliefs. Though there are clashes between people, the culture of every tribe is celebrated and respected. Hence, every culture has its traditions and history that are passed down to its descendants either orally or in a written form. Thus, there is the existence of the concept of pluralism and multiple truths. The destruction of most of the artefacts and records of our ancient scriptures during invasions is a fact that cannot be denied. The epics, vedas, puranas, and upanishads are the records of the lives of legends. It is we, who are unable to perceive the greatness in our tradition owing to westernisation. The stories are narrated from various perspectives emphasising different themes. Hence, the literary creators are left with massive options for their plot creation. They can choose a minute event and string an awful story. A similar concept is also seen in the Indian narrative devices. The writer narrates the events based on his/her understanding of the text. Indian narratology has resemblances to Western narratology. Akin to Western narratology, Indian narratology has no proper tenets for describing the characteristic features of narratology adopted while writing fiction. As such, a stream does not exist in Indian culture. However, there are various genres similar to this, which explains the narratological devices based on the genre the author chose. The eminent Indian poet and a great scholar Ayyappa Paniker has put forth his opinion in *Indian Narratology* thus, “Unlike the modern encyclopaedias of the West where information is

arranged mostly in the alphabetical order and sometimes in a thematic sequence, which gain is subjected to the order of the alphabet in the concerned language, the Indian Puranas follow a different kind of order, which is less mechanical and more interiorized. One may call this a narratological order as the story is narrated within the story when it is necessary. (Paniker, 29). The narrative models as discussed by the Paniker listed as follows: Vedic/Encrypted, Purana/Saga, Itihasa/Epic, Srikhata/Chain, Anyapadesa/Allegorical, Mahakavya/Grand narrative, Buddhist/Jain narrative, Dravidian Model, Folk/Tribal narrative, and miscellaneous narrative.

Amish Tripathi was born and brought up in a Brahmanical family. He was an atheist at a young age but became an ardent devotee of Lord Shiva with time. He has authored ten books, out of which seven books belong to myth fiction, a chronicle fiction, and two nonfiction. His works have been translated into many Indian and International languages. He is popularly known as a literary popstar. To list a few of his awards such as Dwarka Prasad Agarwal Award at the Jaipur Literature Fest (2024), Aaj Tak Sahitya Jagruti Popular Writer Award (2023), Exquisite Art Award at the 21st Century Icon Awards (2021) and many others.

Shiva Trilogy revolves around the protagonist's quest to destroy evil. *Immortals of Meluha* is the first volume in the trilogy. Shiva, the protagonist, is also the chief of the Guna¹ tribe. They migrate to Meluha² on Nandi's³ invitation. Gunas are astounded looking at the beauty and harmony of Meluha. During their quarantine period, Shiva is discovered to be the Neelkanth⁴, the saviour of Meluha. The plot of the story begins with the discovery of Neelkanth. He is presented before the Emperor Daksha for examination. The emperor declares that he is the true Neelkanth after examining the neck. However, there is no public announcement due to Shiva's restriction. Emperor Daksha narrates to Shiva the origin, rules, and customs of his kingdom and finally, discusses the need for a saviour in their well-established society. Shiva witnesses a few attacks on Meluha in his presence and then agrees to the emperor's plea to announce the arrival of Neelkanth. Shiva is sent on a journey to understand Meluha with a few officials and a caravan. During their journey, they encountered another naga⁵ attack. Sati, daughter of emperor Daksha, whom Shiva loved, is injured with a poisonous arrow in the combat. Daksha celebrated the wedding of Shiva and Sati grandiosely. Unfortunately, there is an explosion on Mount Mandar⁶, on the last day of their wedding ceremony. While investigating the remnants, Shiva found the emblem which belongs to a naga. An emissary is sent to Emperor Dilipa, King of Chandravanshis⁷, and war is announced disregarding the reply of Emperor Dilipa. Meluhan's won the war, but they couldn't find any naga in the enemy's cavalry. Meanwhile, Shiva understood that Chandravanshis' are different and are not evil. His guilt increased even more on learning that like Meluhans Swadweepans also believed in the arrival of legend or saviour.

The paper now delves into analysing the narrative techniques that Amish Tripathi has used in *Immortals of Meluha*. The study is an amalgamation of Western and Indian narrative devices. The study primarily focuses on Western devices and then concentrates on Indian narrative devices. The author has employed various narrative techniques to grab the audience's interest. He has used it judiciously in arousing the reader's emotions which carries a sense of connection to the reader. He cleverly uses the journey as a technique in the trilogy, as we see the protagonist is on a continuous journey to discover evil. Thus, we find different settings in the work. The sensory images or the visual description of the scenes present the reader to move in a trance landing into the creator's world. The description is given

prominence in narration as it includes focalization. As Mieke Bal opines that, the textual description uses delimitation, motivation, and rhetoric description. The author has adopted this technique as the readers find description to a large extent. However, the novel is not just narrated on a description basis as we find events and actions happening in the novel. Thus, the descriptions of landscapes and habits of the people are described or narrated to the protagonist by altering various characters in the novel as narrators. The description of the construction of the cities, and marketplaces, and the portrayal of the war scenes are a few of the examples regarding this context. One such description is detailed when the Gunas' enter one of the boundaries of the Meluhan kingdom.

“The vast valley was covered by a lush green canvas of grass. On it was painted the masterpiece that was Kashmir. Rows upon rows of flowers arrayed all god's colours, their brilliance broken only by the soaring Chinar trees, offering a majestic, yet warm Kashmiri welcome. The melodious singing of the birds calmed the exhausted ears of Shiva's tribe, accustomed only to the rude howling of icy mountain winds.” (Tripathi, 11).

The theory of story and narration concentrates on discussing the aspects related to time, causality, and focalization. The writer shifts the chronology to meet his purpose. The story starts when Shiva is twenty years old. Hence, most of the details are presented to the readers using the flashback technique by various characters. Shiva's decision to help Meluhans' is connected to his childhood memory. Though there are multiple references to the haunted past, the memory is not disclosed in this book. When Meluhan's approach to help, the conversation between Shiva and his childhood friend, Bhadra, exposes the emotional weight of this unresolved memory, as he says on page 29, “I can't bear the guilt of running away once again.” The reference is again brought up when Brahaspati, a renowned scientist in Meluha, warns Shiva about the usage of Marijuana.

“Shiva lit up his chillum, took a deep drag and continued, ‘They are scared of not forgetting’. Brahaspati stared sharply at Shiva, wondering what terrible past could have prompted his friend to get addicted to the weed.” (Tripathi, 171)

Furthermore, while recalling Shiva's childhood, he constantly remembers his uncle's words about his destiny. Thus, the author foreshadows the legend he meant to be. The description of the origin of the Meluhan civilization, their system, and their practices are also narrated using the flashback technique by Emperor Daksha. Point of view helps the reader understand the character's real intentions. The author has an entangled point of view and uses the inner voice judiciously. It creates tension in the reader by providing information beforehand at times. The novel ends with a twisting turn as the author adopts red herring and cliffhanger techniques. Cliffhanger is a plot device that creates tension and lets the audience know what happens shortly. For instance, in chapter eight, the author hints at the attack at Mount Mandar which is exposed in chapter ten. “At a short distance from the royal procession, hidden by the dense forest, a small band of fifty soldiers slunk along silently. (Tripathi, 133).

“I am sure that we can come back to kidnap her later. We are dangerously outnumbered in any case. We can't do anything right now.’

The hooded figure replied calmly, ‘Vishwadyumna, have I ordered an attack? Where does the question of us being outnumbered come in? And we are going in the direction of Mount Mandar. A few hours delay will not bring the heavens down. For now, we follow.’” (Tripathi, 134).

In chapter ten, the author details the terrorist attack of kidnapping Sati on their return from Mount Mandar.

“Shiva was about take a second helping of rice when he heard the crack of a twig down the road... Shiva immediately put his plate down, pulled out his sword and fixed his shield on his back. The Arishtanemi were battle ready in a matter of seconds. Sati and Nandi too pulled out their swords and got into traditional fighter positions.” (Tripathi, 158).

Red herring is another literary device which is used to mislead the audience. Both these techniques are fused while describing Chandravanshis’. Towards the end of the novel, Shiva understands that they are different but not evil. “‘But I did not destroy evil!’ yelled Shiva. ‘These people aren’t evil. They’re just different. Being different isn’t evil.’”(Tripathi, 394). Hence, the novel ends with the start of Shiva’s journey to know what evil is, in reality. “‘You are required for the most crucial task: To answer that most important question.’ ‘What?’ ‘What is evil?’” (Tripathi, 396). Applied narratology discusses the concepts of various theories intertwined in the novel. In *The Immortals of Meluha*, we find marginalisation, though we have many portrayals of a Utopian society. The work can be analysed through the lens of neo-historicism, as we find relevance to one of the ancient Indian civilisations. At the outset, the author has created the plot during the era of Indus Valley Civilisation. Most probably during its mature phase, i.e., the golden age of Indus Valley Civilisation. “1900 B.C. at Mount Kailash, near Manasarovar Lake in Tibet.” (Tripathi, 1). Archetypal criticism cannot be excluded as it is a rewriting of *Shiva Purana*. Psychoanalytic criticism also plays a pivotal role because the reason behind the actions of the protagonist is best understood through his dreams which exposes his guilt complex.

The study now shifts to analysing Indian narrative devices, as mentioned earlier. The distinctive features that Indian narratology employs in its literary works like poetry, drama, and folk tales apart from music, theatre, and painting are listed as follows. They are interiorization, serialisation, fantasisation, cyclicalisation, allegorisation, anonymization, timelessness, spatialization, stylization, and improvisation. (Panniker, 4). Interiorisation is a technique, where a story has numerous concepts concealed in it. At the outset, it could be a simple surface but when dealt deeper it intertwines with numerous aspects. “Surface simplicity is a clever device to interiorize a deeper and more complex end.” (Panniker, 5). For instance, the text, *Immortals of Meluha*, revolves around the discovery of evil. Furthermore, it focuses on defining the term evil. The author here encloses the fact that humans are neither good nor evil. However, their principles, belief systems, and their actions determine their relation with them. Apart from this, it discusses the ancient Indus Valley civilization and the existence of the Saraswati River. It also concentrates on the importance of order and harmony for creating a balanced society. The reader is subjected to understanding the importance of embracing different cultures. Owing to this, he discusses the role played by freedom and rigidity in a balanced society as well as sustaining balance in the society. Serialisation is often considered loose in structure by Westerners. Meanwhile, it is celebrated as one of the peculiar

qualities of Indian narrative devices. This technique provides openness and adaptability to the literary creators.

“The episodic looseness of the Indian narrative allows for variations in tone and style in the middle of the work; even gaps are provided for as part of the system; and whenever necessary, a song, dance, and a variety show could be inserted to fill the gaps when it is felt necessary.” (Panniker, 7).

Tripathi has employed episodic structure in narration. This is aptly devised during the conversation between Shiva and Daksha, where Daksha narrates the history of Meluha and the emergence of the saviour to the land. It is employed as a technique to make the readers understand the experience. They are narrated by the emperor Daksha in an episodic way.

“ ‘So where were we, my Lord?’ ... ‘We were about to discuss the change that Lord Ram brought about, your highness ... answered Shiva.’” (IMM, 97). “ ‘Well,’ continued a concerned Daksha, ‘we were talking about the changes that Lord Ram brought about in the society.’” (IMM, 107).

The dance performances of Shiva and Sati are inserted in between the conversations of Daksha and Shiva. This insertion is aimed at easing Shiva’s mind after the conversation with Daksha. “Thanking Daksha profusely, Shiva left the room with Nandi in tow. Shiva approached the hedge with excitement and trepidation ... ‘So good to see you again, Shiva,’ ...” (Tripathi, 103). The concepts of cyclicalisation and fantasisation are adopted in recreating the same plot. It can also be considered as defamiliarization in Western terminology. The author has introduced numerous fictitious elements apart from sketching the events from ancient scriptures. The somras manufacturing unit is fictitious, though it represents contemporary pharma companies. The device allegory, undoubtedly, entertains and educates the reader with its surface and latent content. Devices such as stylization and improvisation should be used judiciously. The word judiciously is used intentionally as an excessive use of these techniques deteriorates the essence of the work. “Stylisation is discipline, improvisation is freedom ... Total stylization is stifling and uncreative, while total improvisation means chaos and is unproductive.” (Panniker, 16, 17).

The author has taken liberty in portraying Sati as a widow, the duel between Tarak and Sati, and portraying Dilipa as the emperor of Chandravanshis, all of which are contradictions according to our sacred scriptures. While reading the Indian narratology devices, it is obvious that the characteristics of puranic narrative coincide with some of the narrative devices employed by the author. The assumption is strengthened by the fact that the teachings of Lord Shiva and his characteristics are narrated mostly in Puranic texts such as *Shiva Puran*, *Linga Puran*, and others. Hence, it can be considered as one of the reasons for his use of the Puranic narrative style in his Shiva trilogy. Puranas can be related to an encyclopaedia. In the West, the encyclopaedia is composed based on the alphabetical order. The narratological order of Indian *Puranas* is less mechanical and more interiorized as the story is narrated within the story when it is appropriate. (Panniker, 29). The author, Tripathi, has employed peculiar qualities of the Puranic narrative in his work. The definition of Purana is mentioned as follows:

“Sargasca pratisargasca

Vamso manvantarani

Vamsanucaritam caiva

Puranam panchalakshanam” (Panniker, 42)

However, the text cannot be compared to the Puranic model, yet there are a few concepts like narrating about the creation, Lord Manu, and the history of dynasties. The stories are narrated to the protagonist, Shiva, an immigrant to Meluha who is discovered to be the saviour of Meluha. Shiva is startled when he is asked for help to save the nation which appears to be close to a perfect society. Shiva learns from Daksha about the somras, saptrishis, Ramrajya, Chandravanshi. In addition, the story of Lord Manu is narrated by Brahaspati and many more. The distinguishing characteristics of the Puranic narrative are listed as follows. They are contextualization, orality, question and answer pattern, use of dialogues, recursiveness, author as character, human-divine interaction, supra-national, and benefits of listening. (Panniker, 30). A few of these devices are analysed below.

The element of contextualization is an important aspect of any story. The narration primarily serves to inform the characters and the audience about an unknown event. The story is told in the context of an emergency, and the characters must be aware of the circumstances. The author used contextualization to persuade Shiva to attack the Chandravanshis. Shiva's desire to understand the necessity for a saviour in such an ideal and educated civilization has driven him to listen to the narrative of Meluha.

‘Why should this bloody blue throat change anything?’

‘You will discover the reason soon enough, my Lord,’ whispered Ayurvati with her head bowed. We have waited for centuries for you.’ (Tripathi, 32).

The use of dialogue also plays an effective role. Like Bhagavata Purana, the text also includes internal and outer dialogue and other usages.

“... on the one level, there is the dialogue within the narrative-internal dialogue, as it were between characters within the story; on the other level, there is the dialogue outside the main story- the outer dialogue, between the narrator and the audience.” (Paniker 33)

The internal dialogues are written in quotations. For instance on page 4, “ ‘POSITIONS!’ screamed Shiva, as he drew his sword.” The outer dialogues are the descriptions and the other essential information that the author narrates through the narrator to the audience. This is seen on page 1, “Shiva gazed at the orange sky. The clouds hovering above Manasarovar had just parted to reveal the setting sun...” The inner voice is placed in italics. It is referred to on page 2, “*God bless Badhra! At least he takes some responsibility.*”. Tripathi has successfully incorporated human-divine connections in the form of question-and-answer sequences. However, the divine is represented here by the wise old man's archetype, thus making their conversations philosophical and enriching. One of the most notable aspects of the Puranic tale is the importance of listening. The protagonist doesn't receive instructions directly; rather, he discovers them by linking the hints with the help of the gathered information during his journey.

“ ‘Your journey is not over, my friend. Not by a long shot. It has just begun. You have to go on. Otherwise evil will triumph.’

Shiva’s eyes cleared up a bit. His burden didn’t feel any lighter, but he felt strong enough to carry it. He had to keep walking to the very end.” (IMM, 398).

“Shiva stared at the Pandit, absorbing the implications of this information. He frowned as one inference suddenly occurred to him. ‘Did the Mahadev’s also leave some tribes behind? Did Lord Rudra?’

The Pandit smiled, deeply impressed by Shiva’s intellect. The Mohan Jo Daro Secretary was correct. *This man is capable of being a Mahadev.*” (IMM, 399)

Conclusion:

A theory is limited based on its characteristic features. Instead of looking at it as a theory, narratology can be considered a process. It focuses on the textual representation, fabula, or the story. The formalist approach is the stepping stone for the enlargement of narratology techniques and devices. Contemporary narratology discusses all the aspects of literary art. It embraces adopting interdisciplinary subjects and various literary theories while narrating the events. It also focuses on the intertextual elements described in the work apart from emphasizing the classification of events and story narration. (*Narratology: An Introduction*, 2014). The research paper emphasizes upholding the view that, the multiple meanings or multiple narratives emerge from the narrator’s sense of narrating the story based on their association with entities, locale, sect, and allies. This has been well depicted in the novel by two different cults called Suryavanshis and Chandravanshis. The writer also throws a light on the existence of multiplicity in the records of history. Dr. Kapil Kapoor emphasizes on the nineteenth century western intellectuals who propounded theories based on insights from Sanskrit texts. The researcher opines that the concepts exist but with different names. The author has imbibed both techniques to suit his purpose in the narration. Finally, the study advocates the element of uniqueness in every culture and the heart to adapt to the differences rather than treating the other as slaves. Though the countries are free from colonial rule, they are deeply rooted in the slavery attitude. This has been one of the reasons for ignoring the rich traditions hidden in any native culture. The recent excavations on Mesopotamia, Egypt, and Indus Valley civilizations have been pieces of evidence for the magnificence of the ancient cultures. India is also one such nation. The accounts have been buried and destroyed when the nation has been a victim of different invasions. The practices based on some scientific or logical reasons have turned into mere superstitious beliefs as the reasoning has been lost due to disconnection with the culture. Any concept or theory that is Westernized is embraced and the others are considered to be barbaric and uncivilized. It is a thought that is deeply rooted in most parts of the world. This study is an attempt to glorify and celebrate the uniqueness of any narrative by vindicating its indigenosity. “... that what is outside their culture is no culture.” (Paniker, 7). It has been the world of the West. However, there is no delay in being a torch bearer by explaining and elucidating the theories and concepts existing in any native culture. The representation of novel direction in the emergence of ancient and unexplored narrative forms in the modern-day needs to be studied. Narrative helps us better visualize

the consequences of cultural change. It is important to thoroughly analyse the texts' substance along with linguistic content. To comprehend the texts', the reader's comprehension should be receptive to philosophical, spiritual, and various interpretations. Thus, the research paper accentuates the importance and emergence of looking into native culture even though adopting other cultures. The disconnection of roots makes a native, a foreigner, as they become alien to their own cultural practices!

Endnotes:

¹ They are one of the mountain tribes near the lake Manasarovar. They face frequent attacks from the other tribes. Manobhu, the previous chief, is assassinated during a peace treaty conference. Hence, Shiva is elected as their new chief. They migrate to Meluha to get rid of these pointless battles.

² It is a kingdom, located in the parts of Pakistan that extends its range from Kashmir to Rajasthan. Lord Ram established the dynasty. The people in this dynasty follow the solar calendar. Hence, they are also known as Suryavanshi. Their motto is truth, duty, and honour. Daksha is the present emperor of the kingdom.

³ One of the captains of Meluhan army. He turned into a true devotee of Shiva after the discovery of neelkanth.

⁴ It is a belief in the Sapt-sindhu⁸ region that, when evil is flourishing to the highest, then a saviour emerges. There are two conditions in finding the neelkanth. Firstly, the person should not be from Sapt-Sindhu. Secondly, the throat turns blue when he drinks somras. Thus, he is called Neelkanth, one with a blue throat.

⁵ The author has defined them as serpent people. However, the description and portrayal of nagas are completely different. They are physically outgrowing people, who have extra limbs for instance. They are considered to be evil, terrorists and cursed people. It is believed that they are born with deformities due to their past life sins. They are exiled from Sapt-sindhu region. They are talented and courageous.

⁶ It is the place where somras is manufactured. Meluhans treat it as the 'heart of Meluha'. The medicine rejuvenates people's energy and acts as a detoxifying agent by removing free- radicals from the body. Hence, people can experience a long life as it balances the aging factor.

⁷ They are the rivals of Suryavanshi. They follow a lunar calendar and thus, they are called Chandravanshis. Their motto is passion, beauty, and freedom. This region includes northeast parts of India up to Ayodhya. They are also known as Swadweepan, which means 'Land of Islands'.

⁸ It is the region covered with the land of seven rivers. Both Suryavanshi and Chandravanshi are situated in this region.

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